

Synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of manganese-, iron-, cobalt- and nickel(II) with some disubstituted pyridines and catechol

Rashmi Sharma and R. S. Sindhu*

Department of Chemistry, Regional Institute of Education, Bhopal-462 013, India

E-mail : drrssindhuncert@yahoo.com Fax : 91-755-661668

Manuscript received 7 January 2002, revised 20 November 2002, accepted 16 April 2003

Mixed ligand complexes of the type $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{M}(\text{L}_1)_2\text{L}_2]$; $\text{M} = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Fe}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II} , $\text{HL}_1 = 2,3\text{-dihydroxypyridine}$ or $2\text{-amino-3-hydroxypyridine}$; $\text{H}_2\text{L}_2 = \text{catechol}$, have been synthesized. All the complexes have octahedral geometry. Thermal stability, order of reaction, apparent activation energy and heat of reaction have been determined. The thermal stability order with respect to metal is, $\text{Mn} < \text{Fe} < \text{Co} < \text{Ni}$.

Role of complex compounds in biological systems is manifested by the presence of either biometals, bioligands or both. That is why different workers^{1,2} are engaged in synthesizing these types of complexes, characterizing them and studying the possibility of their applications in biological and pharmaceutical fields. To add further knowledge in this field, we synthesized the mixed ligand complexes of 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) or 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP) as one ligand and catechol (CTL) as second ligand with bivalent metals. DHP³, AHP⁴ and CTL⁵ are biologically very important ligands.

Results and discussion

On the basis of elemental analyses (Table 1) the composition of the mixed ligand complexes can be assigned as $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{M}(\text{L}_1)_2\text{L}_2]$; $\text{M} = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Fe}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II} , $\text{HL}_1 = \text{DHP}$ or AHP ; $\text{H}_2\text{L}_2 = \text{CTL}$. The complexes are insoluble in water but moderately soluble in CCl_4 . The presence of NH_4^+ in the complexes was further confirmed when the reaction of complexes with NaOH gave smell of ammonia.

In the IR spectra of free DHP and free catechol a broad band at $3200\text{--}3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to phenolic OH disappeared in all metal complexes showing simultaneous deprotonation and formation of $\text{M}\text{--}\text{O}$ bond at 3-position of DHP and 1 and 2 position of catechol. A strong band at 1625 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) shifted to lower side ($1603\text{--}1605\text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggesting that DHP (it exists in the forms **I** and **II** but the form **II** predominates⁶) coordinates to metal through oxygen

Table 1. Physical data of complexes^a

Compd.*	Colour	Yield %	Dec. temp. °C	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Mn}(\text{DHP})_2\text{CTL}]$	Brown	63	190	14.0 (13.2)
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Fe}(\text{DHP})_2\text{CTL}]$	Black	67	200	12.8 (13.4)
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Co}(\text{DHP})_2\text{CTL}]$	Black	59	205	13.8 (14.0)
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Ni}(\text{DHP})_2\text{CTL}]$	Brown	65	210	12.9 (14.0)
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Mn}(\text{AHP})_2\text{CTL}]$	Green	61	195	14.8 (13.1)
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Fe}(\text{AHP})_2\text{CTL}]$	Brown	64	215	12.6 (13.3)
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Co}(\text{AHP})_2\text{CTL}]$	Black	58	220	13.1 (13.9)
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Ni}(\text{AHP})_2\text{CTL}]$	Green	65	225	12.7 (13.9)

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

*DHP and AHP after loss of one H atom and CTL after loss of two H atoms.

of carbonyl group at 2-position also. A relatively weak band at 3400 cm^{-1} observed in free DHP and attributed to ν_{NH} of α -pyridone like structure of DHP remained unchanged in complexes suggesting its non-involvement in coordination. $\text{M}\text{--}\text{O}$ bonding was further confirmed due to the presence of a band⁷ at $450\text{--}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In the IR spectra of AHP three bands at 3425 cm^{-1} , 3375 cm^{-1} and 3125 cm^{-1} are assigned due to ν_{OH} ($\text{O}\text{--}\text{H}\cdots\text{N}$), ν_{NH} asymmetric and ν_{NH} symmetric vibrations respectively. In catechol a broad band at $3200\text{--}3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ appears cor-

responding to ν_{OH} . On complex formation the band corresponding to ν_{OH} in catechol and AHP disappeared indicating that oxygen atom of phenolic groups (two in catechol and one in AHP) are coordinated with the central metal ion. The bands corresponding to ν_{NH} asymmetric and ν_{NH} symmetric were shifted to lower side by 40–30 cm^{-1} indicating that N of amino group of AHP is coordinated to metal atom. The M–O⁷ and M–N^{7–10} bond formations were further confirmed by the presence of bands and 450–600 cm^{-1} and 400–450 cm^{-1} respectively.

Electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes display four weak absorption bands at 30510, 29100, 24100 and 19607 cm^{-1} in case of Mn-DHP-CTL complex and 30580, 29200, 24180 and 20290 cm^{-1} in case of Mn-AHP-CTL complex. These bands may be assigned as ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$ (4G) (10B + 5C), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ (4D) (17B + 5C), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}$ (4G) (10B + 5C), and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (4P) (7B + 5C) transitions respectively indicating octahedral geometry¹¹. The bands at 18870 and 18910 cm^{-1} observed in Fe^{II} mixed ligand complexes with DHP-CTL and AHP-CTL respectively are attributed to ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ transition which support octahedral geometry around Fe^{II} ion in both the complexes. In the spectra of Co^{II} complexes two bands were observed at 18520 and 22200 cm^{-1} in DHP-CTL complexes and 18600 and 22300 cm^{-1} in AHP-CTL complexes. These may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}$ (F) \rightarrow ${}^4A_{2g}$ (F) (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}$ (F) \rightarrow ${}^4T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3) respectively. These bands suggest octahedral geometry around Co^{II} ion¹².

Ni^{II} complexes showed only one band at 17240 cm^{-1} (Ni-DHP-CTL) and 17260 cm^{-1} (Ni-AHP-CTL) which may be attributed to ${}^3A_{2g}$ (F) \rightarrow ${}^3T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2). The range of this transition¹³ suggests octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} iron.

The ESR spectra of Mn^{II} mixed ligand complexes gave one broad isotropic signal carried around approximately free electron g -value. The g_{av} values calculated are 1.992 for Mn-DHP-CTL and 1.996 for Mn-AHP-CTL. From the g_{av} values it is observed that with respect to ligands DHP and AHP the order is AHP > DHP. The values are indicative of some M–L covalent character. The broadening of the signal in the spectrum may be due to spin-relaxation.

TG curves of all complexes showed that the latter decomposed in one step only leaving a stable residue whose weight was in appreciable agreement with the calculated weight of metal oxide (Mn₃O₄, Fe₃O₄, Co₃O₄ or NiO formed from respective metal complexes). From the comparison of initial decomposition temperatures, it is inferred that the order of thermal stability of the complexes with respect to metal is, Mn < Fe < Co < Ni. The finding is in consonant with the Irving-Williams order¹⁴ for bivalent metal ion complexes.

The calculations of activation energy and order of reaction were performed by graphical method of Coats and Redfern¹⁵. The order of reaction in each case was 1. The activation energy values followed the order with respect to metal as Mn^{II} < Fe^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} which is same order as witnessed in case of thermal stabilities of complexes.

DTA curve of each complex showed only one exothermic peak. This large and broad peak is assigned due to simultaneous decomposition, oxidation, reduction, combustion processes of the complex and leading to formation of metal oxide. The heat of reaction (ΔH) for each complex was calculated as suggested by Borchardt and Daniels¹⁶. From the values of heat of reaction, it was inferred that the order with respect to metal for same ligand is Mn^{II} < Fe^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II}. The same order had been found in case of thermal stability and activation energy.

Experimental

The salts of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} or Ni^{II} and ligands DHP or AHP and CTL were taken in the molar ratio 1 : 2 : 1 (M : DHP/AHP : CTL). To the metallic salt dissolved in distilled water (50 ml) the ligands were added slowly with constant stirring, maintaining pH ~9.0 by adding ammonia. The mixture was refluxed on water bath for 1–1.5 h. On concentrating and cooling, the complex separated out which was filtered and dried over P₄O₁₀.

The metal contents were determined by standard methods¹⁷. C, H and N were analyzed at R.R.L., Bhopal. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (CCl₄) were measured on a Backman DU-64 spectrophotometer and ESR spectra on a Varian V-4502-12 ESR spectrometer using DPPH at $g = 2.0023$. TG and DTA curves were recorded using a Red Croft STA-780 thermal analyzer at a heating rate of 10°/min in an atmosphere of air with a flow rate of 60–70 ml/min using α -alumina as a reference material.

References

1. G. Valli, S. Sivakolunthu, M. Thirumalai Kumar, S. Muthusubramanian and S. Shivasubramanian *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 79.
2. K. Syamasundar and M. Adharvana Chary, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 32.
3. C. Houghton, K. A. Wright and R. B. Coin, *Biochem. J.*, 1968, **106**, 51.
4. G. Gerald, F. Christine and B. Jacqueline, Eu/Pat. PE, 412899/1991 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1991, **115**, 8828).
5. J. O. Howton and G. F. Reynold, *J. Polarographic Soc.*, 1965, **11**, 53.
6. B. Penfold, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1953, **6**, 591.
7. C. J. Patenik and D. W. Wester, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 864.

Note

8. L. I. Katzu, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **75**, 467.
9. R. C. A. King, E. Korrs and S. M. Nolson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 5449; 1964, 4832.
10. D. E. Scaifo and K. R. Wood, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 358.
11. C. J. Herdt, C. F. Koster and A. N. Johnson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 6471.
12. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968.
13. R. G. Devota, G. Ponticelli and C. Preti, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1633.
14. H. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746.
15. A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 68.
16. H. J. Borchardt and F. Daniels, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4.
17. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th. ed., Longmans Green, London, 1978.